

Software Unit Tests

Commissioning of software units

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1. Introduction

This document describes unit tests and software used to build up the final software control loop for the platform. Source code is available under following Gitlab project:

<https://gitlab.ost.ch/ost-robotics-buchs/slingload>

2. Sensors

Tests sources available under: <https://gitlab.ost.ch/ost-robotics-buchs/slingload/-/tree/master/test>

	Folder	Executable names
Thread IMU Data	sbg_imu	test_sbg test_sbg_minimal
Thread Laserscanner Data	rplidar	rplidar_test
Thread Baumer Sensors	baumer	test_baumer
Thread Realsense	realsense	realsense_test Depth/ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • get_depth_test • pointcloud Multicam/ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • multicam • track_depth Tracking/ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • t265_pose_img • tracking_pose Trajectory/ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • t265_trajectory
All sensors running with transforms to Platform reference system	sensorfusion	Test_sf

3. Observers

Folder for matlab data: 12_Software/01 observers

Tests sources available under: <https://gitlab.ost.ch/ost-robotics-buchs/slingload/-/tree/master/test/control>

	Folder	Executable names
Observer Acc2Pos	control	Obs_acc2pos
Observer Vel2Pos	control	Obs_vel2pos
Observer X, Y, Theta	control	Obs

3.1 Position estimation from acceleration

3.2 Position estimation from velocity

3.3 Global Observer for estimation (x, y, phi)

4. Odrives

4.1 Speed Setpoint, USB interface Test

EEROS sources: https://gitlab.ost.ch/ost-robotics-buchs/slingload/-/tree/master/test/odrive_usb

4.2 Speed step response

EEROS sources: https://gitlab.ost.ch/ost-robotics-buchs/slingload/-/tree/master/test/odrive_step_response

Folder for matlab data: 12_Software/02 odrive_step_response

4.3 Speed setpoint, thrust calculation, two motors

EEROS sources: https://gitlab.ost.ch/ost-robotics-buchs/slingload/-/tree/master/test/odrive_x2

4.4 Thrust setpoint, two motors

EEROS sources: https://gitlab.ost.ch/ost-robotics-buchs/slingload/-/tree/master/test/odrive_thrust_setpoint

4.5 Force setpoint, eight motors

EEROS sources: https://gitlab.ost.ch/ost-robotics-buchs/slingload/-/tree/master/test/odrive_x8_fxyz

Folder for matlab data: 12_Software/03 odrive_x8_fxyz_ref

5. Position control

5.1 Position control, feedback from distance sensors

EEROS sources: https://gitlab.ost.ch/ost-robotics-buchs/slingload/-/tree/master/test/pos_ctrl_baumer

Folder for matlab data: 12_Software/11_pos_ctrl_baumer

PD Controller $f_0 = 1$ Hz

PD Controller $f_0 = 3 \text{ Hz}$

5.2 Position control, feedback from observer (distance sensors + IMU)

EEROS sources: https://gitlab.ost.ch/ost-robotics-buchs/slingload/-/tree/master/test/pos_ctrl_baumer_imu

Folder for matlab data:

- 12_Software\11 pos_ctrl_baumer
- 12_Software\12 pos_ctrl_baumer_imu
- 12_Software\13 pos_ctrl_baumer_imu_with_lpf
 - o Low pass filter introduced after Baumer Sensors acquisition block
 - o See also: 12_Software\05 baumer_pos_est_with_internal_filter (filters in baumer tool)
 - o See also: 12_Software\06 baumer_pos_est_with_eeros_filter (eeros low pass filter)
- 12_Software\14 pos_ctrl_baumer_imu_cascaded
 - o PD Control loop implemented as cascaded control loop
- 12_Software\15 pos_ctrl_baumer_imu_inclination
 - o Integration of "Transform IMU Inclination", to correct imu signals with platform inclination
 - o See also basic test: 12_Software\04 imu_inclination_compensation
- 12_Software\16 pos_ctrl_baumer_imu_derivatives
 - o Investigation of problems with derivatives, connected to use of Transition blocks (need to define execution sequence of periodics)
- 12_Software\pos_ctrl_baumer_imu_final
 - o Final implementation and parameter tuning

Final Configuration:

Baumer Data acquisition

- Free Running
- Very High Filter (default setting)

Low Pass Filter in EEROS for d1, d2, d3

- Alpha = 0.2 ($out = in * alpha + (1-alpha) * out_old$)

PD-Controller

- Cascaded
- P-Gain with Root Curve (Wurzelkurve)

5.3 Position control, feedback from observer (distance sensors + IMU + Laser)

EEROS sources:

- https://gitlab.ost.ch/ost-robotics-buchs/slingload/-/tree/master/test/pos_ctrl_baumer_imu_laser
- https://gitlab.ost.ch/ost-robotics-buchs/slingload/-/tree/master/test/rplidar_edge_detection

Folder for matlab data:

- 12_Software\18 pos_ctrl_baumer_imu_final
- 12_Software\07 rplidar_column_detection: basic software and algorithms for columns detection

6. Final software

6.1 Position control, feedback from observer (Distance Sensors + IMU)

EEROS sources: https://gitlab.ost.ch/ost-robotics-buchs/slingload/-/tree/master/app_lab_baumer

Folder for matlab data: 12_Software\19_app_lab_baumer

Test path

Test path with external disturbances:

XY Plot without and with disturbances

6.2 Position control, feedback from observer (Laser + IMU)

EEROS sources: https://gitlab.ost.ch/ost-robotics-buchs/slingload/-/tree/master/app_lab_laser

Folder for matlab data: 12_Software\20 app_lab_laser

Test path:

6.3 Position control, feedback from observer (Pixy Camera + IMU)

EEROS sources: https://gitlab.ost.ch/ost-robotics-buchs/slingload/-/tree/master/test/app_lab_camera

Folder for matlab data: 12_Software\21 app_lab_camera

Test path

Test path with disturbances

